

PHIRI

Population Health Information
Research Infrastructure

Deliverable D8.3: FAQ-List: Archive of rapid responses from research to policy

17.03.2021

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This project has received
funding from the European
Union's Horizon 2020
research and innovation
programme under grant
agreement No 101018317

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D8.3, the FAQ list of the Rapid Exchange Forum (REF), is currently available only at the members-only platform “SharePoint” of the project but in the long run most of this information will be published on the official EU Health Information Portal (www.healthinformation.eu) which will be launched in Q2/2021.

The excel file includes all topics covered in the REF meeting and all participants can access and adapt the file. It includes an overview file stating the following information:

- Number of the REF meeting (column A):
“Running” number of the REF meetings
- Question/topic keyword (column B):
Keywords are defined in order to quickly search the questions/topics covered in the meetings, e.g. mass testing, vaccination strategy, Variants of Concern.
- Question/topic (column C):
This field includes the questions(s)/topic(s) covered in the meetings including all subquestions. Questions are linked to the excel spreadsheets that include the relevant country information given.
- Date (column D):
Give the date of the REF meeting where the topic was discussed.
- Name of excel sheet (column E)
Column E includes the name of the excel spreadsheet where country information on the respective question/topic is included.
- Last update (column F)
Column F includes the last update of the country information given.

In the next step selected information generated in the SharePoint (e.g. based on information collected in the bi-weekly REF meetings (cf. D8.2) will be uploaded by GÖG and/or Sciensano to the Health Information Portal and shared with the interested public.

Screenshot SharePoint:

WP 8 - Rapid Exchange Forum

WP8 docs

+ new document or drag files here

✓	Name	Modified
	COVID-19 deaths	... February 4
	Duration of Quarantine and Isolation	... March 1
	ICT	... January 18
	Output	... December 1, 2020
	REF - Special edition	... February 15
	REF meeting agendas	... February 3
	REF meeting minutes	... January 19
	REF meeting presentations	... March 8
	FAQ_all_REF	... 6 days ago

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Screenshot FAQ:

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G
1	REF N	Question keyword	Question	Date	Name of excel sheet	Last update (country)	
2	1	Testing strategy/Preparations for winter	What are the testing strategies currently in your country? How is your country preparing for winter in relation to COVID-19?	16.11.2020	Current testing strategy (1 REF)	25.11.2020	NOTE: Countries that respond
3	2	Vaccine prioritization	Vaccine prioritisation lists – target groups: Order of target groups (1. HCWF, 2. vuln groups...) Where do young people who are vulnerable fit in?	30.11.2020	Vaccine prioritization (2 REF)	05.01.2021	
4	2	Mass testing	Experiences on mass testing	30.11.2020	Mass testing (2 REF)	05.01.2021	
5	3	Counting of RAT	Counting of Rapid Antigen Tests. Are negative tests captured too? Are they included with the number of tests reported to ECDC on TESSy? Are cases detected on Rapid Antigen Tests included in the case notification numbers?	14.12.2020	Counting of RAT (3 REF)	11.01.2021	
6	3	Update on COVID-19-diagnostics	Update on COVID-19 diagnostics (strategy, ongoing projects, policy direction) - especially children strategies	14.12.2021	Update on diagnostics (3 REF)	11.01.2021	
7	4	RAT tests	Are RAT tests being used to: 1. Find more cases to ask to isolate 2. Allow test negative people to do things which otherwise would not be allowed e.g. fly, visit care homes and hospitals, reduce isolation duration	04.01.2021	Use of RAT (4 REF)	27.01.2021	
8	5	Risk classification/traffic light systems	(Regional) risk classification or traffic light systems: Which indicators and thresholds are used in order to change the risk level/class or traffic light of the systems (threshold values and/or ranges of incidences)?	18.01.2021	Risk classification (5 REF)	27.01.2021	
9	5	Measures winter/Christmas 2020	Measures around Christmas: Have any measures been taken before Winter/Christmas to better prepare the Healthcare system for the 3rd wave? (e.g. new beds/infrastructure/hiring new people)	18.02.2021	Measures winter 2020 (5 REF)	27.01.2021	
10	6	Moribund COVID-19 patients	Protocols/procedures in moribund COVID-19 patients: Are there specific protocols or procedures for the treatment of moribund COVID-19 patients all the way through death and burial available in your country? If yes, what kind of protocols or procedures are in place/available?	01.02.2021	Moribund patients (6 REF)	11.02.2021	
11	7	Reduction in infection rates in vaccinated persons	Is there any reduction in infection rates in vaccinated persons already visible?	15.02.2021	Infection rate in vacc.(7 REF)	01.03.2021	
12	8	Variants of concern	What is the percentage of the variants of infections? Has your country implemented specific regulations concerning isolation/quarantine or testing for people who are (or are suspected to be) infected with a variant of concern and/or their contacts? (e.g. longer isolation/quarantine; additional testing).	01.03.2021	Variants of concern (8 REF)	10.03.2021	

REF overview

Current testing strategy(1 REF)

Vaccine prioritization (2 REF)

Mass testing (2 REF)

Counting of RAT ...

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